

Speech is Golden

- on ASR at the service of the Danish public sector

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L1 speakers	2.2 mio	5.5 mio
EU working language	yes	yes
Mix of municipalities	5-6 city / many small	4 city / 94 small

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	Slovene	Danish
Inflected language	>>English	>English
Compounding	>English	>English
Rich in vowel qualities	>English	>>English

This talk

1. Why ASR in the municipalities?
2. ASR - the technology
3. Trough of disillusionment
4. The new alliance

Why ASR in the Danish municipalities?

The local authorities smelled a business case...

The slick salesman:

- 1) economy! - the medical case
- 2) speech aid for the challenged
- 3) 'welfare tech' - assisting in difficult working situations

The technology looked extremely user friendly and mature

[ad]

On top of that, the *real* world had embraced ASR already

Gartner hype curve

2010 EMERGING

Years to mainstream adoption:

- less than 2 years
- 2 to 5 years
- 5 to 10 years
- ▲ more than 10 years
- ⊗ before plateau
- obsolete

tazti speech recognition software

Now on Sale

Sale: ~~\$89.00~~ \$39.99

[BUY NOW](#)

All NEW
Dragon Dictate
for Mac, v4

However, it did not go so smoothly!

A quick intro to ASR

ASR - the technology

Three central components

- Acoustic model (**AM**)
- Language model (**LM**)
- Search engine referring to **AM** og **LM**

Acoustic model

A set of recognizers, one for each language sound ('phone')

Language model

- Unigrams
- Bigrams
- Trigrams
- (n-grams)

all frequency annotated (NB! corpus-driven)

UNIGRAMS:

the > is > in > cat > oven

BIGRAMS:

the cat > the fat >>> *the that >>> **the sat

Language model

- Unigrams
- Bigrams
- Trigrams
- (n-grams)

all frequency annotated (NB! corpus-driven)

UNIGRAMS:

the > is > in > cat > oven

BIGRAMS:

the cat	About 89.400.000 results
the fat	About 40.100.000 results
the that	About 10.300.000 results
the sat	About 7.020.000 results

(by Google)

TRIGRAMS:

is in the >> in the oven >> ...

N-GRAMS (domain specific mwe.s)

the cat is on the mat
the cat is in the oven

ASR: a search engine over AM and LM

How are the AM and the LM developed?

Based on annotated corpus data

(tokenized, transcribed, tagged, time-coded)

Example: the speech corpus

[rec]

↑ ↑ ↑ ↑ ↑ ↔ ↑
the **cat** **is** **in** **the** **oven**

the	cat	is	in	the	oven
DH AH0	K AE1 T	IH1 Z	IH0 N	DH IH1	AH1-V-AH0-N
0 140	170 210 280	350 480	680 810	1010 1260	1310 ????

(phonetic script: cmu dict)

[play]

Training data

Acoustic model materials	size (order of mag.)
phonetic dictionary	100,000 lemmas
speech recordings (multi-speaker)	100 hours
speech recordings (focus users)	1 hour each

Language model materials	size (order of mag.)
text corpus (general)	100M words
text corpus (specific for professional area)	100k words
non-linguistic tokens (forms, symbols, ...)	100 documents

back on track...

Status as of 2011

ASR contracts by 2011

Vendors: **4**

KMD
IBM Denmark
PDC Dictus
Max Manus

Technological suppliers: **1**

Investors (municipalities): **22**

Positive business-cases:

ASR contracts by 2011

Vendors: **4**

KMD
IBM Denmark
PDC Dictus
Max Manus

Technological suppliers: **1**

Investors (municipalities): **22**

Positive business-cases: **0**

Did Gartner lie?

Maybe not,

but several things conspired against the municipalities:

- Danish has difficult words: long, inflected, ...
- Danish has difficult vowels: lenitions, reductions, assimilations, ...
- MONOPOLY

The case of Odense

(they did everything right)

Odense features

- Three year budget
- Dedicated project leader
- Training programme for employees
- 900+ participants = North-Europe's biggest

Odense did everything right - and failed

- Inflated expectations - 'savings' already entered in next-year budget!
- No clear HR policy (few employees liked ASR, most gave up)
- Vendors soon vanished: Poor service after contract was signed
- Extremely slow updates (waiting 24 months for new context files)

At project end, ~150 active users (<20%)

2010 EMERGING

Danish version
2011

The new alliance

The new alliance

Steering committee

- OS2 (50+ Danish municipalities, 100% flat organization)
- DanCAST (Copenhagen Business School)

Advisory board

- KOMBIT (independent advisor)
- CST (Copenhagen University)
- Danish Parliament (Folketinget)
- Danish National Broadcast (Danmarks Radio)

First action point: Recycling of resources

Opaque module structure

Similar experiences everywhere

- all keep paying for the same resources (e.g. phonetic lexicon)
- loss of ownership to own data (e.g. annotated speech files)
- licence lock-in (change product = begin from scratch)
- no knowledge transfer (data exchange barred)

Recycling corpus materials

Acoustic model materials	size (order of mag.)	recycled?
phonetic dictionary	100,000 lemmas	yes
speech recordings (multi-speaker)	100 hours	yes
speech recordings (specific users)	1 hour each	no

Language model materials	size (order of mag.)	recycled?
text corpus (general)	100,000,000 words	yes
text corpus (specific)	100,000 words	no
non-linguistic tokens (forms, symbols, ...)	100 documents	partly

Optimal recycling of training data

Recyclable : Project specific = **50 : 1**

Drawing the line between mine and yours

The toolbox

(all is open domain)

<i>Tools (assorted)</i>	<i>Status 2016</i>
OCR scanner	OK
De-formatting	OK
Tokenizer	OK *
Anonymizer	OK ***
Symbols (num, abbrev, ...)	OK **

(*) = needs localization

Example: Raw document to structured text

14217031952C15238

05.08.2014

Syddjurs Kommune
 Team Byggeri
 Hovedgaden 77
 8410 Rønde
 Afdelingens hovednr.: 8753 5510

Syddjurs Kommune Team Byggeri Hovedgaden 77 8410 Rønde	Ejendomsnummer	Bygn.nr.	Vokode	Husnr.	B	Etage
	1827		928	20		
	Societetsnr.		Ejerskabsnr.		Byggesagsnummer	
				13/40386		

Erklæring fra autoriseret VVS-mester

Undertegnede autoriserede mester erklærer at have udført følgende arbejder efter gældende bestemmelser:

VVS-arbejde

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Vand- og sanitetsarbejder	<input type="checkbox"/> Gas installationer	<input type="checkbox"/> Andet, angiv art
Alt: _____		

på ejendommen

Vej navn (inkl. bopælsgade)	Husnummer
Kaprifolievøj	20
Løst vedligeholdelse	
9 DL EGGSMARK BY, DRÅBY	
Ejerskabstype	
Byggesedens dato	
09.01.2014	Arbejdet færdigt den
	4-7-2014

Evt. bemærkninger

Er der sket ændringer i forhold til det godkendte projekt, skal der sammen med denne erklæring fremsendes reviderede tegninger m.v.

Dato og underskrift	
Dato	Aut. mesters stempe/ og underskrift
4-8-2014	 A/S Auning Blikkenslagerforretning Vestergade 46 E, 8963 Auning Tlf. 86 48 41 72
CVR nr.	
14235094	
Autorisationsnr.	Ejernes adresse
VFUL - 00450	Kaasumygdal.dk
Mødest.	
14696000	

Krupp Print System A/S
Bilskema E-C140-726 - Side 9 af 7

After OCR scanning

Syddjurs Kommune
Team Byggeri
Hovedgaden 77
8410 Rande
Afdelingens hovednr: 8753 5510

Undertegnede autoriserede mester erklærer at have udført følgende arbejder efter gældende bestemmelser:

WS-arbejde
VA Vand- og ksanitetsarbejder I Gasinstallationer på ejendommen

Ejer/bygherre
Byggeliladelsens dato Arbejdet færdigt den 09.01.2014

Preparing anonymization

Syddjurs Kommune

Team Byggeri

Hovedgaden 77

8410 Rande

Afdelingens hovednr: 8753 5510

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Ejer/bygherre

Byggeliladelsens dato Arbejdet færdigt den 09.01.2014

Text preparation: Tokenizing, normalizing, anonymizing, ...

Prognose og behandlingsmuligheder:

Der er klar **overensstemmelse** mellem de objektive fund og borgers fortælling..

- Foreligger der lægeskøn eller udtalelse fra egen læge ang. **pronose**,
arb evne mm?

Ja. Egen læge ser ikke noget arbejdsmarkedsperspektiv for **Marianne**.

prognose og behandlingsmuligheder _

der er klar overensstemmelse mellem de objektive fund og borgers fortælling

foreligger der lægeskøn eller udtalelse fra egen læge angående prognose
arbejdsevne med mere

ja

egen læge ser ikke noget arbejdsmarkedsperspektiv for _FirstName_

Second action point: Preparing generic specs and documents

Documents available in generic/embryonic forms:

Databehandlertaftaler ("data processing agreement")

Systemkrav ("system requirements", specs)

Udbudsmaterialer ("bidding materials")

...

Third action point: Managing the bidding situation

Bidding material should specify

- clear division of components (dictionary, AM, LM)
- transparent recycling (reused vs. new data)
- only latest-state of databases can be owned by provider
- short update-cycle for AM and LM

Either as requirements or as desiderata

Bidding material should refer to the shared corpora, e.g. qualification round

These features are as important for **return-of-investment** as are WER etc.

The HUB

www.dancast.dk

The DanCAST hub for ASR localization support

Status quo 2016

May 2015: First 100% Danish-Danish contract
Januar 2016: First independent SME established
July 2016: Now 3 Danish SME start-ups

Neither would have existed without the shared HUB-data

Bidding rounds are now more fair (results not given in advance)

Economically most significant result:

Licence conditions are vastly improved,
even in *old* contracts!

So, a happy end?

Not entirely:

Government cuts in 2015 and 2016 in all public budgets
Also universities are currently firing researchers

However:

The HUB survives and is now almost self-sustaining

By way of conclusion

If we could start over...

Step 1. Prepare the ground

IT responsables: Nuts-and-bolts courses
Decision makers: Adjusted expectations!
End-users: interest groups for employees

Step 2. Collect existing materials

Corpora
Tools for annotation, alignment, tagging, anonymization, ...

Step 3. Establish a data portal

Restricted entry - for individual municipalities
Semi-restricted entry - data-sharing among municipalities
Unrestricted entry - fully processed and anonymized data

Step 4. Create a library of generic formulas (semi-restricted access)

Agreements, tender material, specs

Step 5. Prepare for bidding rounds

Organize groups of municipalities

Require!

THE END

